

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES:

Figure S1. Aerial photogrammetric of study area in Krakal-Sadranan, Yogyakarta south coast, Indonesia.;

Figure S2: Syringe cementation test scheme;

Figure S3: Electrical and multi analysis surface wave results of α -section. (A1) the resistivity of line 4, (B1) the MASW of line 4, (A2) the resistivity of line 5, and (B2) the MASW of line 5.;

Figure S4: Three dimensional of beachrock model calculation based on geophysical statistical anomaly data from electrical resistivity and multi analysis surface wave of β -section.

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